

WaysTUP!

VALUE CHAINS FOR DISRUPTIVE TRANSFORMATION OF URBAN
BIOWASTE INTO BIOBASED PRODUCTS IN THE CITY CONTEXT

D3.15: Report on demonstration of PILOT 6 (Final)

WP3 – Demonstration of urban biowaste utilization through PILOTS operation

Authors: Marcos Latorre, Caterina Coll (PERSEO); Aleta Duque, Ignacio Ballesteros, M^a José Negro, Raquel Iglesias (CIEMAT); Julia Hereza, Carlos Albarrilla (AMB); Peter Stipsitz (TBWR).

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Other authors	Aleta Duque, Ignacio Ballesteros, M ^a José Negro, Raquel Iglesias (CIEMAT); Caterina Coll (PERSEO); Julia Hereza, Carlos Albarrilla (AMB); Peter Stipsitz (TBWR)		
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Executive summary

This deliverable reports on the work done in Task 3.7 of WAYSTUP project, regarding the demonstration activities of Pilot 6. This is the Final Report on Task 3.7 (M48), reported as an update of intermediate report which was submitted in M31 of the project (D3.7). In this pilot, the cellulosic rejection stream selected in Task 2.7 (i.e residual paper and cardboard from municipal waste treatment plants) has been evaluated for the production of bioethanol. This bioethanol was used as a chemical intermediate to be further converted into the biosolvent ethyl lactate.

The pre-treatment of paper and cardboard (P&C) for bioethanol production (disintegration) was improved at lab scale by decreasing the amount of required additives, increasing the amount of solids in the process and reusing the washing liquid, resulting in a considerable reduction of water consumption. It was observed that the filtrate from the disintegration step could be reutilized in the saccharification and fermentation steps, since it does not have any detrimental effect for these two bioprocesses. Moreover, the liquid recovered after the disintegration could be recycled up to 3 times within the process without greatly affecting the enzymatic digestibility of the pretreated solids. Moreover, a new tailor-made enzymatic cocktail of enzymes to treat the P&C substrate was developed and used in demonstration trials. Regarding fermentation, it was concluded that addition of nutrients to the medium was unnecessary, and that the inoculum size could be reduced by 25-50% without affecting the final yield of ethanol.

Demo activities at PERSEO plant were carried out using the new 10m³ pre-treatment reactor specially designed to work with P&C, and a 50m³ fermenter. Optimized laboratory conditions in terms of additive doses, enzymes, temperature, pH and times were used in the demo trials, and up to 4 tons of substrate were used in one fermentation batch, leading to a volume of 18 m³ at 15% TS. A 57% ethanol yield (compared to the theoretical one) was obtained (less than 10% lower than that in the parallel laboratory control), achieving the objective set. The corresponding bioethanol potential was 135 L bioethanol/ton of P&C waste. The biomethane potential of the byproducts from the alcoholic fermentation was evaluated, showing a great potential to be valorised by means of anaerobic digestion technology.

Regarding ethyl lactate production, reactive distillation was optimised at laboratory level and successfully scaled-up. Reactive distillation was successfully demonstrated at a capacity of 4.5 L/h ethyl lactate and a product purity of >96 w%. The process was optimized towards energy efficiency. Compared to the industrial process of ethyl lactate production, energy savings of 1.8 MJ/kg ethyl lactate are expected by using the optimised reactive distillation process.

1. Pilot Overview and Objective

This deliverable reports on Task 3.7 Utilisation of rejections from MSW treatment plants (MSWTP) for bioethanol and biosolvent (Pilot 6: PERSEO). The main objective of this task is to demonstrate at semi-industrial scale the viability of bioethanol and ethyl lactate production from cellulosic rejections from MSWTP.

First part of PILOT 6 was located in L'Alcudia (Valencia, Spain), in the biotechnological demonstration plant of PERSEO (PERSEO Bioethanol[®] plant). In this Pilot, three types of material were studied at lab-scale along Task 2.7. These materials included cellulosic waste materials from municipal waste and wastewater treatment plants (WWTP) from Barcelona Metropolitan Area (AMB). In particular, the three types of materials studied were sanitary textiles, P&C and cellulosic rejections (mainly WWTP wipes).

After the lab evaluation and main optimizations (see D2.7), the blend of food-contaminated P&C material was selected to be used in the demonstration activities in WP3. The reasons for this selection mainly relied on the fact that contaminated P&C from MSWTP i) is one of the materials with the highest carbohydrates content (57%) and therefore with the highest bioethanol potential; ii) has a similar enzymatic digestibility than the other two raw materials after the adequate pre-treatment, and iii) is the cellulosic material generated in higher amounts in the waste treatment plants from a volume generation point of view.

The activities in this task included a further study for the optimization of the bioethanol production at lab scale carried out by CIEMAT and PERSEO. In Task 2.7, the plant was adapted to the requirements of the project with the implementation of a new 10m³ pre-treatment reactor specially designed to treat P&C material. In this task, this reactor has been used for the demonstration activities on the production of bioethanol from this cellulosic waste.

To complete the process flow of Pilot 6, the bioethanol produced was evaluated by TBWR partner to produce the biosolvent ethyl lactate through a reactive distillation prototype located in Linz (Austria). The materials flow of PILOT 6 in WP3 is illustrated below in **Figure 1**.

Figure 1. General overview of the Pilot 6 operation.

2. Logistics for biowaste supply

The AMB is in charge of the collection and supply of biowaste for PILOT 6.

The feedstock chosen for the Pilot's demonstration is obtained from the municipal waste fraction that is not source-separated, specifically, the P&C rejections. This unsorted fraction, from Barcelona City and other municipalities of the Metropolitan Area and surroundings, is collected by each city council and sent to Ecoparc 4, a mechanical and biological treatment plant (**Figure 2**).

Figure 2 Municipality discharging its waste in the Ecoparc 4 pit.

Thus, Ecoparc 4 managed by AMB and located in Els Hostalets de Pierola (Barcelona), has the ability to recover resources such as organic matter and recyclable materials from urban waste rejections, specifically those found in the unsorted waste container, not source-sorted. One of the materials being recovered is the contaminated P&C, which currently cannot be reintroduced into the market for recycling due to its low quality. This fraction is the one sent to PERSEO in PILOT 6 (**Figure 3**).

The waste is initially sorted at the AMB's waste treatment plant using both paper optical separators and a ballistic sorter to obtain the aforementioned feedstock for the Pilot. The first type of sorter is programmed to identify objects made of paper and blows to separate them from the main belt along scanning (**Figure 4**), while the second one allows for a gravimetric separation of 2D/3D materials based on a rotary and inclined movement.

Moreover, the process includes a manual sorting. Hence, several workers make sure that the materials already sorted by automated means are not mixed up, so as they swap any material that has been placed on the wrong belt.

Figure 3. Cardboard and paper waste sorted at Ecoparc 4 and sent to PERSEO in PILOT 6.

Figure 4. Paper optical separators in Ecoparc 4.

For each demonstration trial, it was expected to sort, pack and ship around 4 tonnes of P&C rejections. This semi-industrial scale samples were sent to PERSEO around every three months, with a total of eight batches.

According to the Law 9/2017, of November 8, on Public Sector Contracts, AMB started an abbreviated simplified open procedure to contract the service of biowaste shipping from Ecoparc 4 for Pilot 6. Thus, AMB requests the transport company to send the biowaste at least 1 week in advance to PERSEO facilities.

3. Bioethanol production

3.1 Laboratory optimization

3.1.1 Characterization of different batches of feedstock

The chemical composition of the selected feedstock (contaminated P&C) was continuously monitored through the project in order to evaluate its variability and the potential effects on the pre-treatment. Every new batch of samples was analyzed following the methodology established in deliverable "D1.1: Laboratory analysis protocol and methodology for executing WAC". Previously, three batches of samples were analyzed, as reported in "D1.2: Report on urban biowaste composition & physicochemical characteristics". During the period that covers the present report, twelve more Waste Analysis Campaigns (WAC) were carried out and their corresponding samples were analyzed.

Glucan content varied between 41 and 56% in the fifteen samples analysed, with a mean value slightly above 50% and a relatively low variation between samples. In total, the sum of carbohydrates in P&C samples accounts for more than 58% of the dry weight. Moreover, another 13% of the weight of the samples corresponded to the acid insoluble residue, not hydrolysable. The amount of ash was higher in the first WACs than in later ones, with a final mean value around 15% of the dry mass. High glucan content and low ash amount are supposed to be beneficial for the yield of the process. Indeed, the more carbohydrates in the feedstock, the higher concentrations of sugars could be potentially attained after the pre-treatment.

Apart from the P&C feedstock samples, CIEMAT analysed the composition of two samples from the residue after the conversion of disintegrated P&C to ethanol, and one sample of the cellulose part of sanitary textile. Notably, the samples of residue analysed presented a certain amount of carbohydrates recalcitrant to the saccharification and fermentation processes and had a high moisture content. New valorisation strategies that take into account the high-water content of the residue was considered to fully consume these residual sugars and valorise the ethanol production by-product, such as, wet anaerobic digestion.

The analysis of the sanitary textile (mainly nappies) was consistent with the results of the analysis presented in "D1.2: Report on urban biowaste composition & physicochemical characteristics". Sanitary textile showed a high glucan (cellulose) content; however, it gave some problems due to the absorbent components in the nappies and the analysis protocol had to be adapted.

3.1.2 Optimization of the saccharification

Saccharification of the disintegrated P&C is another key step of the process. Increasing the hydrolysis yield would lead to higher sugar concentrations in the media, thus obtaining higher

ethanol concentrations after the fermentation. In this context, enzyme consumption is a crucial point and the main focus of the activities here reported. A new set of enzymes, especially suitable for treating the kind of substrates here produced, was employed for the next experiments. The solids content for the optimization experiments on saccharification was about 15%.

Firstly, the effect of the enzyme dosage on the saccharification yield of disintegrated P&C was investigated, as shown in **Figure 5**. The hydrolytic enzyme used for these tests will be named Enzyme A from here on.

Figure 5. Glucose concentration in g/L for the different doses of Enzyme A used. D1 was the lowest dose tested and D10 the highest, being D10 approximately ten times the amount of D1.

Figure 5 shows an increasing trend of the glucose concentration with the increase of the enzyme dosage, as expected. The glucose concentration increased to 66 g/L using D10 while only 32 g/L were obtained with D1, which means that in order to double the amount of glucose obtained, the dose of Enzyme A needs to be increased ten times. Finding an equilibrium between the amount of enzyme used and the saccharification yield is very important for the economics of the process. Thus, D3 was selected to continue the work of optimization of the saccharification.

The next experiment was aimed at improving the enzymatic cocktail formulation by studying the combined effect of Enzyme A and the accessory Enzyme B on disintegrated P&C. Both enzymes were supplied by Novozymes company. Four different combinations were tested, varying the proportion of Enzyme B between 0% and 7.5% in weight of the enzymatic preparation. Saccharification tests were run at 15% solids load and 50°C for total 48h (**Figure 6**).

Figure 6. Glucose concentration in g/L obtained from the saccharification of disintegrated P&C with different enzymatic mixtures.

The addition of accessory Enzyme B resulted in a certain increase of the amount of glucose released, as it can be seen in the **Figure 6** above. After 48 h of incubation, the combination 95% A+5% B released about 47 g/L of glucose compared to 43 g/L in the case where no Enzyme B was added. From that point on, the addition of a higher proportion of Enzyme B did not result in an increase of the glucose released, which means that there would be then an excess of the enzymatic activity provided at percentages >5%.

This mixture, 95%A+5%B, was then used for the next experiment, in which the use of a saccharification auxiliary compound proposed by the enzymes supplier was investigated.

Figure 7. Glucose concentration in g/L obtained from the saccharification of disintegrated P&C in the presence of different dosages of the auxiliary compound. d0 means no auxiliary compound was added, d1 was the lowest dosage and d2 the highest.

As it can be seen in **Figure 7**, the use of the auxiliary compound did not improve the saccharification and it had even a negative impact on the yield when the highest dose was added. Therefore, the use of this auxiliary compound is not justified for this substrate.

Lastly, the effect of increasing the incubation temperature of the saccharification with the mixture 95% A+5% B was studied and the results are presented in **Figure 8**.

Figure 8. Glucose concentration in g/L obtained after the saccharification of disintegrated P&C at different temperatures, being $T2 > T1$.

The increase of the temperature caused a remarkable decrease of the glucose released during the saccharification and possibly led to the inactivation of enzymes, since at T2 almost no increase of glucose concentration was observed from 24 to 48h, unlike what happened at T1. The results agree well on the fact that T1 was nearer the average optimum temperature for both enzymes, according to the enzymes supplier.

3.1.3 Optimization of the fermentation

The conversion of fermentable sugars to ethanol is the last part of the process. In this regard, the concentration of the inoculum of the commercial yeast used and the addition of nutrients to the fermentation media were tested.

The effects of the nutrients added on the ethanol production are presented in **Figure 9**. For this experiment, two solid loads, 10 and 15% (w/w), were employed. The substrates were incubated first 24h only with the enzymes and then inoculated, with the addition or not of nutrients to the medium.

Figure 9. Ethanol concentration in g/L obtained from media incubated at 10 or 15% (w/w) solids. Dashed lines indicate that no nutrients were added to the media.

Results showed that the addition of nutrients increased the amount of ethanol produced during the first hours of incubation, but those differences were reduced and eventually disappeared after 24-48h of fermentation. Since the presence of nutrients did not have a significant impact on the final ethanol production, its addition could be avoided for experiments up to 15% (w/w) solids, reducing operational costs of the process.

A different set of experiments was designed to evaluate the influence of the inoculum concentration on the ethanol production. The disintegrated P&C were incubated with enzymes at initial 15% (w/w) solids load for 24h and they were then inoculated and incubated for additional 72h. In this case, five different inoculum concentrations were tested. Results are shown in **Figure 10**.

Figure 10. Ethanol concentration in g/L obtained from saccharification and fermentation experiments carried out with different inoculum concentrations, being "I" the standard inoculum concentration.

Lower inoculum concentration produced less ethanol during the 24 first hours after the inoculation, but again, all the inoculum dosages reached similar concentrations after 48 and 72h of fermentation. No differences were detected between 100% and 75% I, even during the first hours. This means that the inoculum dosage could be reduced at least 25% without decreasing the yield of the process and, depending on the fermentation time, this reduction could be even greater (50% to 75%).

3.2 Demonstration activities

3.2.1 Process description

Based on the lab results for bioethanol production from P&C, PERSEO made a preliminary scale up in a 50 L pilot reactor before the demo activities at higher scale. Several experiments varying the solids concentration (up to 15% w/w), enzymes load and fermentation times were carried out with a 50 L bioreactor (**Figure 11**).

Figure 11. Experiments for the production of bioethanol from P&C up to 15% solids in 50L reactor.

The pre-treatment processes were also proved to be key in the 50 L pilot reactor to achieve higher ethanol production yields from the P&C feedstock. This pre-treatment has indeed an impact in the enzymatic hydrolysis (EH) yield, since the EH yield significantly improved from $39.5 \pm 2.5\%$ for the condition without pre-treatment to $56.0 \pm 2.0\%$ for the one with optimal pretreatment.

Pilot tests for bioethanol production using sanitary textiles as feedstock

In previous *Deliverable 2.7 Report on preparation of Pilot 6*, not only P&C material was studied at lab scale, but also other two cellulosic wastes: sanitary textiles from MSWTP and WWTP wipes. Food-contaminated P&C was selected to be used in the demonstration activities in WP3 due to different reasons already explained (it is the material with highest bioethanol potential). The second material with highest potential for bioethanol production is sanitary textiles, since it contains around double amount of carbohydrates compared to WWTP wipes.

After the selection of the raw material for process optimisation and scaling up in the pilot plant, the following steps were taken. The logistics for waste collection, the separation method as well as demo operation were optimized for P&C material. However, it was considered also interesting (and proposed by the PO) to make some scale up tests for the bioethanol production from sanitary textiles (nappies) from lab to 50 L pilot reactor. Thus, pilot tests at 50 L scale optimizing bioethanol production using this cellulosic waste have been performed. In particular, two main parameters were evaluated:

- The % Total Solids (TS) at which this material can be used, with the target of increasing up to 15% TS.
- The impact of the hydrothermal pretreatment in the bioethanol production yield.

The pretreatment of sanitary textiles was evaluated at lab scale in Task 2.7, showing that the best conditions yielded to around 80% of enzymatic digestibility of the glucan content.

Nappies represent a growing problem for municipalities since they are produced in large amounts and are not currently valorised. In Spain, a baby spends an average of 6 nappies a day, which means that they use 5.400 nappies during their first 30 months of life (estimated time a baby uses nappies). This means more than one tonne of waste during these two and a half years.¹

Nappies are mainly composed of polymers (PE, PP, around 30% wt), cellulose (35% wt) and a superabsorbent polymer (SAP) (35% wt). The cellulose fraction can be hydrolysed into glucose and fermented to produce bioethanol. A 50 Kg sample of waste nappies (from a kindergarten) was sent to PERSEO by AMB and they were milled and homogenized in a pilot mill (**Figure 12**). Samples were sterilized in autoclave before any manipulation during trials.

¹ <https://www.conasi.eu/blog/consejos-de-salud/panales-desechables-ecologicos/>

Figure 12. Waste nappies received at PERSEO facilities from collection by AMB (left) and the milled material (right)

This material, which contained 40% of glucan (d.b) and 53% humidity was evaluated for bioethanol production at pilot scale (50 L bioreactor). An acid pretreatment using optimized conditions in the lab was used. The results showed that this pretreatment improved the enzymatic hydrolysis of glucose (**Table 5**). Higher dosages of acid did not show any improvements in the enzymatic hydrolysis yield. Different solid loadings were tested and the maximum reached was 12% TS. This material, as expected, is very hygroscopic and absorbs a lot of water due to the presence of the SAP, leading to a gel that impedes to work at higher solids concentrations (**Figure 13**).

Figure 13. 50 L bioreactor with waste nappies and the gel formed during the tests

Results indicate that the acid pre-treatment is necessary to improve the enzymatic hydrolysis (EH) yield, which was 77% at 5% total solids loading and decreases as total solids increases to 12%. The high fermentation yields indicate that the SAP polymer and organic residues are not causing inhibition to fermentative microorganisms and cellulose fraction is being hydrolyzed and fermented. However, the other fractions of nappies (plastics, SAP) limit the operability and performance of the whole process. In conclusion, for an efficient valorisation of nappies, a mechanical or chemical pretreatment should be carried out in order to separate the cellulosic and polymeric fractions before performing the biological conversion of the contained cellulose.

In the case of P&C material, the information obtained along lab and pilot trials was useful to adapt different equipments of PERSEO demo plant and properly work with the P&C feedstock, already reported in previous D2.7. **Figure 14** shows some pictures of PERSEO plant.

Figure 14. Pictures of PERSEO Bioethanol® demo plant.

The design of the new 10 m³ pre-treatment unit for P&C valorisation was described in D2.7, while the complete implementation of the reactor in the plant can be seen in **Figure 15**.

Figure 15. Pictures of the new 10 m³ pre-treatment system installed at PERSEO plant.

3.2.2 Results of demonstration activities

The demo activities were carried out using the new 10 m³ pre-treatment reactor installed for WaysTUP project, specially designed to work with P&C.

The main aspects to consider when dealing with this raw material at demonstrative level are:

- To carry out a dry milling and powerful pulping (wet milling) in the reactor to effectively break the paper fibers and disintegrate the material.
- To use the optimal dose and tailor-made enzymatic cocktails to improve the rheology of the mix and reduce viscosity, especially at high solids content.
- To set a tight pH control, since the variation of pH with this substrate can be high

AMB supplied to PERSEO with 8 different P&C waste batches of several tons at their facilities

(Figure 16):

- 25/11/2021 – 3.96 t
- 16/02/2022 – 4.00 t
- 09/05/2022 – 4.00 t
- 13/06/2022 – 4.00 t
- 03/10/2022 – 4.58 t
- 28/11/2022 – 4.56 t
- 27/02/2023 – 4.52 t
- 19/06/2023 – 5.74 t

Figure 16. Discharge of 4 tons of contaminated P&C from AMB at PERSEO facilities.

Once discharged, the materials were milled, homogenized and a small amount (around 1 kg) was sent to CIEMAT laboratories for chemical characterization (**Figure 17**).

Figure 17. Reception of paper from AMB, milling and sterilization in bags prior chemical characterization by CIEMAT.

The most important parameters that impact overall on the bioethanol potential per ton of P&C are total glucan (around 50% in dry basis), moisture (25-35%) and inert materials (15-20% w.b.). In order to know the amount of inert materials contained in the paper and cardboard (mainly plastics and textiles), a manual sorting was done for the estimation, thus obtaining around 15-20% weight of such materials in all batches (**Figure 18**).

Figure 18. P&C and inert materials (mainly plastics, textiles) after the manual sorting of the material received at PERSEO.

In **Figure 19** it can be seen some pictures of the demonstration activities performed for the production of bioethanol from P&C. The material is discharged in the reception area and then milled. After milling, it is transported through the conveyor belt where the main inert materials and ferrous metals are removed manually and with an automatic rotating magnet, respectively. The inert materials are reduced to less than 7% (on a wet basis). Then, the material is sent to the reactor by a screw system, where it is mixed with water and enzymes. Here the pre-hydrolysis takes place at 50°C. Later, the broth is cooled down and is sent to the fermenter of the PERSEO plant (50 m³ total volume).

Figure 19. Lift of P&C in the mill (left) and manual sorting of inert materials before sending it to the 10 m³ reactor (right). 50 m³ fermenters in PERSEO plant where bioethanol fermentation takes place (down)

Optimized laboratory conditions in terms of additive doses, enzymes, temperature, pH and times were used in the tests and up to 4 tons of substrate were used in one fermentation batch.

Trials started at 11% TS and were progressively increasing to 15% TS (set as objective in DoA), while maintaining the ethanol yield. As the percentage of total solids increase the volume of fermentation decreases when treating 4 ton of substrate in each batch, leading to a volume of 18 m³ at 15% TS. At the same time, the concentration of ethanol in the fermentation broth also increases with the solids load.

Regarding simultaneous saccharification and fermentation (SSF) yield, the objective was to have at demo scale a difference of less than 10% compared to the lab control (set as 60% yield), thus having the objective of at least 55% SSF yield. A value of 57 % of SSF yield was obtained, thus achieving this performance target too.

Assuming this yield and the average composition of P&C material indicated in Table 1 (29.5% moisture, 50.7 %glucan in dry basis) the bioethanol potential of this material is 190 L bioethanol/ton dry raw material (**135 L ethanol / wet P&C ton**). This value is significantly high when compared with alternative substrates such as the organic fraction of municipal solid waste, due to the high glucan content of this raw material and lower humidity.

Finally, samples of the bioethanol distilled from the demo trials were sent to TBWR for validation and comparison with commercial ethanol for the production of the biosolvent ethyl lactate.

Biomethane potential of fermentation by-products

It was considered interesting to evaluate the valorisation of bioethanol process byproducts by means of anaerobic digestion. Thus, AMB studied the biomethanation potential (BMP) of some Pilot 6 rejections in order to know if biomethane production could be a potential technology to valorize the byproducts generated during the alcoholic fermentation of P&C waste. These byproducts correspond to the solid and liquid residues from the bioethanol production process (**Figure 20**). During the last period of the project, 3 batches of samples were taken from demo trials in PERSEO plant and sent to AMB for analysis to an external laboratory:

- Nov - 2022:
 - Solid fraction (output) – 3 kg
 - Liquid fraction (output) – 1.5 L
- Dec - 2022:
 - P&C (input) – 0.6 kg
 - Solid fraction (output) – 2 kg
 - Liquid fraction (output)– 3 L
- Mar - 2023:
 - P&C (input) – 2 kg
 - Solid fraction (output) – 3 kg
 - Liquid fraction (output) – 3 L

Figure 20. Pictures of waste P&C feedstock (left) and solid and liquid byproducts from the bioethanol production process

The results indicated that biomethanation potential still exists after subjecting the P&C to the bioethanol production process (**Table 1**). As expected, fresh P&C shows higher BMP than residues. Liquid fraction has higher biomethanation potential than the solid one (output) (ex. sample 1: 327 vs 267 L CH₄/kg SV). In any case, the values of BMP obtained are similar to the

ones obtained for OFMSW materials, indicating that anaerobic digestion could be an interesting route to valorise the by-products obtained from the bioethanol production of food contaminated P&C waste.

Table 1. Results of the biomethanation potential. Methane yield and degradation constant of the studied samples (standard variation in brackets)

	Parameter	L CH ₄ /kg SV	k (day ⁻¹)	L CH ₄ /kg sample	L CH ₄ /kg ST
Sample 1 (Nov 22)	Liquid fraction	327 (8)	0,25 (0,03)	19	249
	Solid fraction	267 (37)	0,21 (0,021)	62	230
Sample 2 (Dec 22)	Liquid fraction	340 (16)	0,28 (0,05)	12	259
	Solid fraction	213 (15)	0,17 (0,02)	51	195
	P&C (input)	351 (32)	0,12 (0,03)	192	286
Sample 3 (Mar 23)	Liquid fraction	298 (10)	0,39 (0,07)	22	214
	Solid fraction	240 (22)	0,28 (0,10)	54	205
	P&C (input)	336 (21)	0,13 (0,03)	183	241

4. Ethyl lactate production

To further upgrade bioethanol from P&C waste (and potentially other sources of organic waste), TBWR developed a reactive distillation process to produce the biosolvent ethyl lactate.

4.1 Work plan

The objectives of this activity were:

- The production of a high-value solvent from biowaste.

Ethyl lactate is an established biosolvent for the chemical industry (pharmaceutical, cosmetics, industrial cleaning etc.) with potential for new applications. Compared to conventional petrol-based solvents (such as NMP, MEK, ethyl acetate, isopropanol, glycol ethers, etc.) ethyl lactate offers beneficial properties for worker safety (low vapour pressure, non-toxic) and environment (completely bio-based, readily biodegradable, environmentally benign). It has the potential to substitute the conventional solvents mentioned above in many applications such as solvent for paints, inks and in cleaning products. The use of ethyl lactate instead of fossil-based solvents bears the opportunity to reduce CO₂ emissions due to the short-term carbon cycle and to improve air quality by reducing VOC (volatile organic compounds) emissions. (Pereira et al., 2011) More information can be found in *D5.20 Report on concrete quality characterization and data sheets for the produced ethyl lactate in Pilot 6*.

- Scale-up and demonstration of reactive distillation (target TRL6).

The conventional production process of ethyl lactate is the esterification of lactic acid and ethanol using an acid catalyst (usually sulfuric acid) until the chemical equilibrium is reached and the subsequent separation of the components to obtain ethyl lactate of technical grade (98%). The reaction is controlled by equilibrium, which means that the side-product water limits the reaction rate and feedstock conversion. Therefore, the conventional process is energy demanding and exhibits high production costs. TBWR developed a reactive distillation process as an alternative technology to increase the efficiency of ethyl lactate production and reduce its production costs. The concept of reactive distillation is to intensify the esterification reaction by separating the side-product water from the reaction mixture, as indicated in **Figure 21**. By

combined separation and esterification, a high reaction rate and potentially complete conversion of the feedstock can be achieved.

Figure 21. Concept of process intensification for ethyl lactate production.

Process development in WaysTUP! was based on a prior multi-parameter optimization of reactive distillation, including the feed ratio of ethanol/lactic acid, the catalyst weight fraction, and the distillate rate. Preparatory experiments showed that the energy demand can be reduced by using a decoupled setup for distillation enhanced esterification. The heat required for distillation is reduced by 42% in comparison to an integrated reactive distillation setup (Stipsitz et al., 2021). Therefore, a decoupled setup was chosen as starting point of process optimization. Reactive distillation was scaled-up to pilot scale using existing equipment and demonstrated at TRL6.

- Minimising the energy demand and costs of the overall process.

A reduction of production costs could allow the use of ethyl lactate in a range of new applications, for which the biosolvent is currently considered as too expensive (Pereira et al., 2011). Using feedstock derived from waste streams bears the potential to reduce the material costs. Considering the current energy prices in the EU, energy efficiency is paramount for economically viable production.

The following aspects of the process were optimized in WaysTUP!:

- Feedstock
 - Validation of bioethanol from WaysTUP! partners as a low-cost feedstock.
 - Prevention of lactic acid oligomers to enable optimal resource usage.
 - Evaluation of acceptable water concentration levels in both feedstocks.
- Separation of water
 - Optimization of the overall setup to separate water efficiently from the feedstocks and the reaction mixture.
 - Fast separation for process intensification. Reactive distillation was optimized to reach a high space-time-yield in the reactor, so compact equipment can be used and CAPEX is reduced.

- Purification
 - Vacuum distillation and lactate precipitation were tested to purify ethyl lactate. The objective was to minimize the energy demand without compromising product quality.

Moreover, synergies of integrated production of ethanol and ethyl lactate on the same site were assessed. Finally, a new option for improving energy efficiency was tested, using novel commercial membranes. The potential for further cost reduction by utilizing waste-derived lactic acid was also highlighted.

4.2 Laboratory optimization

In the first optimisation phase, the focus was on the pretreatment of both feedstocks, ethanol and lactic acid. Concentrated lactic acid is not the optimal feedstock for ethyl lactate synthesis. Due to the bifunctional structure, lactic acid molecules form oligomers (shown in **Figure 22**) by intermolecular self-esterification. This chain-forming reaction is promoted at low water fraction.

Figure 22. Structure of lactic acid monomer and oligomers.

The kinetics of oligomerisation and oligomer hydrolysis is slow compared to ethyl lactate formation (Pereira et al., 2008). Therefore, hydrolysed lactic acid feedstock is required to avoid reactant supply limitations. **Figure 23** shows the fraction of lactic acid which is readily available for ethyl lactate production (LA₁) as a function of the overall lactic acid concentration at equilibrium. For commercial lactic acid (88 w%), one third of the feedstock is not accessible for the reaction. As a workaround, two different concentration levels were tested in lab scale experiments: a dilute solution of 26 w% lactic acid and a medium concentration of 65 w% lactic acid. The solutions were equilibrated for 24 h at 80 °C and then, concentrated by vacuum distillation at mild conditions to avoid re-oligomerisation. Vacuum distillation was tested at two different pressure levels (100 mbar and 30 mbar). The effect on oligomerisation and the initial water fraction of the reaction mixture were determined.

Figure 23. Oligomer content at equilibrium as a function of total lactic acid concentration. (Figure adapted from (Vu et al., 2005)); Red: commercial solution (88 w%), orange: low concentration (26 w%), green: medium concentration used for demonstration (65 w%).

The results of lactic acid pretreatment are shown in **Table 2**. When choosing the feedstock for pilot scale, a trade-off between the oligomer level and the effort for pretreatment (energy demand and transportation costs) was considered. A medium concentration of 65 w% lactic acid offers a satisfying compromise: Reactant losses due to oligomerisation were reduced from 33% to 10%. Although the transportation mass of overall lactic acid is 35% higher compared to technical grade (88 w%), the 65 w% solution contains almost the same amount of accessible lactic acid LA_1 . Re-oligomerisation occurred in distillation at ambient pressure (experiment B) but was successfully prevented by vacuum distillation (experiment C and D).

Table 2. Results of lactic acid pretreatment.

Pretreatment experiment	A	B	C	D	E	F
Lactic acid concentration (w/w)	0.88	0.65		0.26		
Vacuum pressure (mbar)	no pretreatment	1013 (ambient)	100	30	100	30
Oligomer frac. in mixture (w/w)	0.124	0.113	0.037	0.039	0.015	0.016
Water frac. in mixture (w/w)	0.051	0.085	0.051	0.016	0.051	0.016
Energy demand (MJ/kg lactic acid)	-	7.2	3.0	4.0	6.3	8.4
Transport mass of total lactic acid (kg/kg lactic acid)	1.14	1.54		3.85		
Transport mass of LA_1 (kg/kg LA_1)	1.70	1.71		3.97		

Regarding ethanol pretreatment, dehydrated ethanol is required as a feedstock for reactive distillation in order to reach significant process intensification (Stipsitz et al., 2021). This is due to the azeotrope at 95 w% ethanol. Below this concentration the flux of water removed by distillation is low and the separation is very inefficient. Ethanol dehydration is an established process at industrial level, and also required for other applications such as the use of ethanol as a biofuel. Two different processes were assessed in WaysTUP!. Firstly, the adsorption of water using molecular sieves (zeolite, 3 Å) and secondly, a membrane separation process (pervaporation). The dehydration of ethanol was possible with both considered processes.

Figure 24. Batch and reactive distillation experiments of ethyl lactate production at laboratory level.

Bioethanol from Pilot 6 was tested for the production of ethyl lactate in lab scale experiments of reactive distillation. **Figure 24** shows the experimental set-up for the laboratory experiments. Process performance was evaluated in terms of ethyl lactate yield. Bioethanol from PERSEO (**Figure 25**) was compared to commercial bioethanol (Australco, Austria) and bioethanol produced by NTUA from source separated biowaste in Pilot 5. All experiments were carried out in triplicate. The results were analyzed using a one-way ANOVA (analysis of variance). There was no statistically significant difference of ethyl lactate yield for the different ethanol samples tested ($F(2,6)=0.76$, $p=0.51$). The catalyst was neither damaged, nor inhibited by the tested ethanol samples. Hence, bioethanol from Pilot 5 and Pilot 6 was successfully validated for the production of the biosolvent ethyl lactate.

Figure 25. Bioethanol sample for validation tests.

The main results of the laboratory optimization are shown in **Table 3**. The yield based on lactic acid was increased from 37% as a reference without pre-treatment to 80% by optimised pre-treatment. The recovery of ethanol from the distillate is essential for efficient operation. At optimal conditions, ethyl lactate yields of 85 % based on lactic acid and >95% based on ethanol were reached.

Table 3. Results of laboratory optimization of ethyl lactate production.

Bioethanol pretreatment	Lactic acid pretreatment	Ethyl lactate yield based on lactic acid	Ethyl lactate yield based on bioethanol
no pretreatment (96% ethanol)	no pretreatment (88 w% lactic acid)	37%	6%
dehydration of ethanol feedstock	hydrolysis, vacuum distillation at 100 mbar	56%	9%
dehydration of ethanol feedstock	hydrolysis, vacuum distillation at 30 mbar	80%	13%
dehydration and recovery of ethanol	hydrolysis, vacuum distillation at 30 mbar	85%	>95%

4.3 Scale-up and Demonstration

The reactive distillation process was scaled up using existing equipment at pilot scale. **Figure 26** shows the overall process of ethyl lactate production. The process consists of feedstock pre-treatment steps followed by reactive distillation as the main process and the downstream

purification. In the pretreatment, both feedstocks are dehydrated. The dehydration of ethanol is also used to recover the fraction which has not been converted into ethyl lactate from the distillate. This dehydration step can be done in the ethanol plant by adsorption of water on molar sieves, using synergies of established infrastructure. A lactic acid feed of medium concentration (65 w%) was used, as a result of feedstock pretreatment tests on laboratory level. It was dehydrated by vacuum distillation in a rotary evaporator at 80 °C and 30 mbar. Immediately after pretreatment, lactic acid was mixed with dehydrated ethanol (99.9%). Feedstock validation showed no significant differences of process performance between bioethanol from Pilot 6 and using commercial bioethanol. As a result, all experiments at pilot scale were conducted with commercial feedstock from a local provider (Australco, Austria) to simplify the supply logistics. In the main process step, the dehydrated feedstock is processed by reactive distillation. By the combined reaction and separation process, the chemical reaction is intensified, and high product yield is achieved. Residual lactic acid in the raw product is separated in a purification step and recycled to the pre-treatment. The final ethyl lactate is obtained as a clear product of high purity. The closed loop setup makes it possible to reach high ethyl lactate yield based on lactic acid as well as bioethanol.

Figure 26. Process flow diagram of ethyl lactate production.

Reactive distillation was demonstrated at a capacity of 4.5 L/h ethyl lactate. A filter vessel of 10 L volume, equipped with a stirrer and a heating jacket with temperature control, was used as reaction equipment (Figure 27). The separation of water was conducted by distillation in a distillation column (Figure 28) and compared to vacuum distillation regarding its energy demand. The distillate was collected, and ethanol losses were substituted by fresh ethanol. Vacuum

distillation in a rotary evaporator at 80 °C and 20 mbar was used as a purification of the raw product. As an alternative purification process, the precipitation of lactate with calcium oxide (CaO) was tested. The chemical compositions of the reaction mixture and final product were measured via HPLC. A detailed characterization of the produced ethyl lactate can be found in *D5.20 Report on concrete quality characterization and data sheets for the produced ethyl lactate in Pilot 6*.

Figure 27. Pilot scale reactor for ethyl lactate production.

Figure 28. Distillation column at pilot scale.

When distillation was conducted at ambient pressure, oligomerisation of lactic acid was observed causing significant yield losses. By vacuum distillation at milder temperature and shorter residence time, oligomerization was prevented, and the energy demand was reduced. An apparatus for vacuum distillation requires higher CAPEX, whereas distillation at ambient pressure requires higher OPEX due to the higher operation temperature and heat losses. At optimized conditions, 85% of lactic acid was converted into ethyl lactate. The concentration of residual lactic acid in the crude product was still too high for most potential applications. Therefore, it was purified by vacuum distillation at 80 °C and 20 mbar (as shown in **Figure 29**) to obtain ethyl lactate of high purity.

Figure 29. Purification of ethyl lactate by vacuum distillation.

The main results of pilot operation are listed in **Table 4**. A total of 20 L ethyl lactate was produced from 25 L bioethanol and 18 L lactic acid in 6 experiments. At the state of development (TRL6) product quality and the reduction of the energy demand was prioritized over maximizing the process capacity.

Table 4. Results of pilot operation for ethyl lactate production.

Performance parameter	Units	Result	Quantified target
Capacity	L/h ethyl lactate	4.5	approx. 5
Yield based on ethanol	-	>95%	-
Yield based on lactic acid	-	>90%	-
Crude product purity	kg/kg	75%	-
Final product purity	kg/kg	>96%	90%

4.4 Optimization to reduce the energy demand

The energy demand of the different processing steps was evaluated and compared in **Figure 30**. The energy demand of lactic acid pretreatment is due to removing water by vacuum distillation. This aspect was already optimized in the laboratory experiments. The energy demand of esterification is mainly caused by heat losses, which can be minimized by thermal insulation and heat integration. The separation of water combined with the recovery of ethanol, as well as the purification of ethyl lactate account for the largest shares and have the largest potential for technological improvement. Therefore, these aspects were the subject of the following optimizations to enhance energy efficiency.

Figure 30. Energy demand of the processing steps for reactive distillation.

4.4.1 Integrated dehydration by pervaporation

In preparatory experiments it was found that a dehydration of ethanol is required for process intensification. As an optimization, TBWR tested the integration of ethanol recovery and reactive separation by direct dehydration of the reaction mixture via pervaporation. In-situ dehydration has the potential to reduce the energy demand, because only water is removed via the membrane instead of a mixture containing ethanol. Membrane-assisted esterification has already been intensively studied in literature (Delgado et al., 2010; Pereira et al., 2010; Zhang et al., 2015). The reported specific permeate fluxes were low at low water concentration ($<1 \text{ kg/m}^2\text{h}$ at water concentration below 10%), limiting the reaction rate. Acid concentration has been limited to ensure membrane stability. Excessive membrane areas and therefore, high CAPEX would be required to intensify the reaction, making the technology economically unattractive. However, recent material development has overcome these limitations. Acid resistant membranes (specified for operation at pH 0.5-8.0) are available on relevant scale. The integration of lactic acid

pretreatment was also evaluated. The overall process with integrated dehydration by pervaporation is shown in **Figure 31**.

Figure 31. Process flow diagram of ethyl lactate production with integrated dehydration by pervaporation.

The tested membranes are designed for operation at temperatures up to 150 °C and a pressure difference of up to 10 bar between the feed and permeate side. In preparatory experiments, the kinetics of the esterification reaction was evaluated at 120 and 140 °C. The molar feed ratio of ethanol/lactic acid was varied. The experiments were conducted with the laboratory scale reactor shown in **Figure 32**. It has a volume of 0.45 L and is equipped with an inclined-blade stirrer and an electrical heating jacket.

Figure 32. Pressure reactor for the lab scale experiments.

The parameters of the individual experiments are listed in **Table 5**. Due to the dynamic of the electrical heating, the time for heating-up varied between the experiments leading to limited reproducibility of the lab scale experiments.

Table 5. Parameters of the lab scale experiments of batch reaction under pressure.

Reaction experiment	C1	C2	C3	C4
Reactant ratio ethanol/lactic acid (mol/mol)	3.0	3.0	2.5	2.0
Reaction temperature (°C)	120	140		
Reaction pressure (bar)	3.3	5.7		
Time for heating-up (min)	9	13	11	11

An increase of temperature increases the reaction rate. The influence of the reactant ratio was of minor importance. The final optimization of reaction time and temperature was done with the bench scale setup shown in **Figure 33**. It has a volume of 5 L and is equipped with an inclined-plate stirrer and an external thermostat with thermal oil. A reaction volume of 3 L was used. At optimized conditions, a space-time-yield of 0.95 kg L⁻¹ h⁻¹ ethyl lactate was reached at 135 °C and 4.9 bar. It was more than doubled compared to the reaction at ambient pressure (0.45 kg L⁻¹

1 h^{-1} ethyl lactate), whereas the energy demand was 23.6% higher, due to increased heat losses at higher temperature. Heat losses are expected to be drastically smaller at industrial scale, due to the lack of thermal insulation of the bench scale reactor and because the ratio of surface area per reactor volume is decreasing with scale.

Figure 33. Pressure reactor for the bench scale experiments.

The parameters for pervaporation experiments were chosen based on the results of the reaction tests and the available vacuum supply for the overall process. The pervaporation tests were conducted using the lab scale apparatus shown in **Figure 34**. The mixtures produced in batch reaction under pressure were used in the experiments. A variation of the water fraction, temperature, vacuum pressure, and operation time was conducted. The permeate flux and membrane selectivity were evaluated.

Figure 34. Lab scale apparatus for pervaporation.

Selectivity and the permeate flux at optimized conditions were satisfactory. Less than 1% of ethanol was lost to the permeate. Potential for energy savings by integrated dehydration was found. To demonstrate membrane stability, additional test with a longer operation period (3-6 months) would be needed.

4.4.2 Optimization of the purification

Regarding the purification of ethyl lactate, a clear product of high quality is obtained by vacuum distillation. However, the heat demand for distillation is high considering the relatively low fraction of impurities. As an alternative, the precipitation of residual lactic acid and oligomers with calcium oxide (CaO) was tested. The concentration of residual acid in the crude product was measured by titration with NaOH (0.1N solution). An equinormal amount of CaO was added gradually and dissolved. The mixture was agitated and kept at a constant temperature of 50 °C in a rotary evaporator (**Figure 35**). Calcium lactate was formed according to (**Eq. 1** and precipitated on the surface of the round bottom flask. Residual ethanol and water were removed by vacuum distillation at 50 °C and 100 mbar. The precipitate was removed with a paper filter (MN 614 ¼, Lactan) or remained on the surface of the flask. Clear ethyl lactate was obtained as final product. The product quality is compared in detail in *D5.20 Report on concrete quality characterization and data sheets for the produced ethyl lactate in Pilot 6*.

Figure 35. Precipitation of lactate with calcium oxide.

The separated calcium lactate was dissolved in dilute sulfuric acid (2.5 mol/L). Gypsum was formed according to (Eq. 2 and separated from the solution by centrifugation (Sorvall SLC-6000, 6000 rpm, 15 min) as shown in Figure 36. The supernatant was recovered lactic acid, which was re-used as a feedstock.

Figure 36. Recovery of lactic acid and separation of gypsum by centrifugation.

The energy demand and environmental impact of the two purification processes cannot be compared directly, because vacuum distillation is energy demanding, whereas the precipitation technology requires energy intensive chemicals (calcium oxide, sulfuric acid). A reasonable

evaluation was done by DRAXIS in the Life Cycle Assessment (LCA). The results can be found in *D5.11 Report on LCA results of new value chains*.

4.5 Outlook

Ethyl lactate production by reactive distillation was successfully demonstrated at a scale of 4.5 L/h. Bioethanol samples from Pilot 5 (NTUA) and Pilot 6 (PERSEO) were validated and performed equally well as commercial ethanol regarding product yield. The feedstock pretreatment, the separation of water to intensify the reaction and the purification were optimized. By closed loop production, nearly full conversion of both feedstocks into ethyl lactate is achieved. Finally, the feasibility of integrating the feedstock pretreatment with the reactive separation process was tested in pervaporation experiments. The results of the optimization towards energy efficiency are shown in **Figure 37**. The energy demand of a batch process was determined by benchmarking experiments on laboratory level, as defined in the GA. However, an accurate benchmark for implementation is the industrial process for ethyl lactate production. Its energy demand was estimated based on literature data (Wang et al., 2022). Energy savings of 1.8 MJ/kg ethyl lactate are expected by using the optimised reactive distillation process. Further potential was determined by the integration of pervaporation.

Figure 37. Comparison of the energy demand of ethyl lactate production with different technologies.

The direct dehydration by pervaporation is the preferred option for further upscaling. The stability of the evaluated membranes should be verified by long term operation (3-6 months). For industrial scale production, the implementation of ethyl lactate production on-site of ethanol

production is beneficial. Keeping transport distances of dangerous goods short and making use of synergies in shared infrastructure and expertise (production in EX-proof zones, storage of dangerous goods, bounded warehouse) can reduce commissioning and logistics effort drastically.

As an outcome of the LCA by DRAXIS, the predominant contribution to the environmental impact of ethyl lactate production in Pilot 6 was the use of commercial lactic acid as a raw material. The conventional production process of lactic acid is energy intensive and produces gypsum as a waste stream. It is estimated that half of the production costs are caused by the downstream processing (DSP) (Alves De Oliveira et al., 2020)(Li et al., 2021). Hence, there is a large potential for improvement in using biobased or waste-derived lactic acid for ethyl lactate production, also considering new DSP technologies that need further process development. Synergies of the extraction of lactic acid from waste streams and the production of ethyl lactate should be investigated in upcoming research activities.

5. Conclusions

The following conclusions can be drawn from the works done in Task 3.7 regarding the demonstration activities of Pilot 6 and reported here:

- The pre-treatment of P&C for bioethanol production (disintegration) was improved at lab-scale by decreasing the amount of additives, increasing the amount of solids in the process and reusing the washing liquid, thus resulting in a considerable water use reduction.
- It was observed that the filtrate from the disintegration step could be reutilized in the saccharification and fermentation steps, since it does not have any detrimental effect to these two bioprocesses. Moreover, the liquid recovered after the disintegration could be recycled up to 3 times to the process without greatly affecting the enzymatic digestibility of the pretreated solids.
- A new cocktail of enzymes, tailor-made for treating P&C substrate was developed and used in the demonstration trials.
- Demo activities at PERSEO plant were carried out using the new 10m³ pre-treatment reactor specially designed to work with P&C, and a 50m³ fermenter. Optimized laboratory conditions in terms of additive doses, enzymes, temperature, pH and times were used in the demo trials, and up to 4 tons of substrate were used in one fermentation batch, leading to a volume of 18 m³ at 15% TS.
- A 57% ethanol yield (compared to the theoretical one) was obtained, just 5% lower than that in the parallel laboratory control, achieving the objective set. The corresponding bioethanol potential was 135 L bioethanol/ton of P&C material.
- The concentration of solids was increased up to 15% as targeted in the project, which resulted in higher ethanol concentrations in the broth.
- The biomethane potential (BMP) of the byproducts from the alcoholic fermentation was evaluated, achieving values of around 320 and 240 L CH₄/kg SV for the liquid and solid fractions, respectively. These values show a great potential to valorise such residual streams by means of anaerobic digestion technology.

- Bioethanol samples from Pilot 5 (NTUA) and Pilot 6 (PERSEO) were validated for ethyl lactate production and performed equal to commercial ethanol regarding the ethyl lactate yield.
- Reactive distillation for the ethyl lactate production was successfully demonstrated at a capacity of 4.5 L/h ethyl lactate and a product purity of >96 w%.
- The process was optimized towards energy efficiency. Compared to the industrial process of ethyl lactate production, energy savings of 1.8 MJ/kg ethyl lactate are expected by using the optimised reactive distillation process. Further potential was determined by integrated dehydration via pervaporation.
- Mayor potential for improving the environmental impact of ethyl lactate production was found in technology development for the extraction of lactic acid. Synergies of the extraction of lactic acid from waste streams and the production of ethyl lactate should be investigated in future research activities.

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